

The molecular gas contents of $z=1.6$ (proto)-cluster galaxies and their last gasp of star formation

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Lee-Brown, Rudnick et al. ApJ in press →

Rudnick et al. submitted to ApJ

← *Noble+Rudnick et al. ApJ in press*

The evolution of the passive fraction at $z < 1$

- Passive fraction evolves at $z < 1$ in mass-dependent way
- Clusters are more quenched than groups at the same epoch

This talk

1. Quenching and stellar populations in $z > 1$ clusters
2. Molecular gas in 4 $z \sim 1.6$ clusters

Understanding the origins of passive galaxies with high redshift clusters

- many (>30) spectroscopically confirmed members
Papovich, et al. + Rudnick 2010; Tanaka et al. (2010); Tran et al. + Rudnick 2015
- 10 orbit WFC3 G102 data
→ membership and rest-frame optical spectra
Lee-Brown, Rudnick, et al. ApJ in press
- Deepest ever JVLA image taken in CO.
105h on source
Rudnick et al. submitted to ApJ

• What are characteristics of passive population?

IRC 0218
XMM-LSS J02182-05102
CLG J02182-05102

Papovich 2010; Papovich et al. + GR 2012

Rest-frame optical spectra of passive galaxies

- Use GI02 to access $D_{n,4000}$ and get redshifts for passive galaxies
- Use $D_{n,4000}$ to constrain relative stellar ages

Passive and Star-forming galaxies

Massive passive galaxies in early clusters

- Many clusters at $z > 1.6$ are dominated by passive galaxies at high stellar mass.
- Clusters are quenched more than the field

Stellar ages and quenching

- Passive cluster galaxies are consistent with $2.3 < z_{\text{form}} < 3$
- No trend of age with stellar mass but trends not ruled out.

Stellar ages and quenching

- Passive cluster galaxies are consistent with $2.3 < z_{\text{form}} < 3$
- No trend of age with stellar mass but trends not ruled out.
- Challenge to reconcile with mass-dependent cluster passive fraction.
- May imply mass redistribution (merging) or fast early quenching

Molecular gas as a tracer of star formation

- SF is best correlated with molecular gas
- Molecular gas is consumed with constant efficiency (Bigiel et al. 2011)

gas surface density at which HI saturates

Krumholz+08,09

Bigiel+ 2008

What drives the overall decline in SFRs with time

- The decline in SFR is mirrored (or caused?) by a decline in gas supply
- Is decline of SF in dense environments driven by the same phenomena (running out of gas)
- Almost no CO observations of high-z dense environments.

- Are we missing important modes of star formation?
- What is SFR- M_{gas} relation in dense environments?
- How does environment regulate the gas supply?

Decarli et al. 2016

Two CO(1-0) detected galaxies in a $z=1.62$ proto-cluster

Rudnick, et al. submitted to ApJ

Fit using MAGPHYS (da Cunha et al. 2008)

- CO-detected galaxies are on/below main sequence

Rudnick, et al. submitted to Apj

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Gas contents

- $M_{\text{gas}} / (M_{\text{gas}} + M_{\text{star}}) = 0.2 - 0.5$
- $M_{\text{gas}}/M_{\text{star}} = 0.2 - 0.8$

Rudnick, et al. submitted to ApJ

- Scaling relations between gas properties and star formation (Genzel+15)

Comparison with Field

- proto-cluster galaxies follow field scaling relations.
- Proto-cluster is highly quenched
- Molecular gas in star-forming galaxies nonetheless looks identical to field

SFR with relation to main sequence

Rudnick, et al. submitted to ApJ

Not all clusters are the same: The power of ALMA

- 200 hours of observation with JVLA = 2 detections
- 8.4 hours of ALMA = 9 detections at CO(2-1) in 3 SpARCS clusters at $z=1.6$

Diversity in gas properties and elevated gas fractions

- SpARCS cluster galaxies have enhanced gas fractions and longer consumption timescales than field
- Different than CLGJ0218 galaxies at similar mass and SFR.

Noble+Rudnick, et al. ApJ in Press

Gas Fractions and Quenching

- Higher gas fractions may be related to lower quiescent fractions.
- We need surveys with gas masses for more galaxies, at many SFRs, and in multiple clusters.

Nantais et al. (2016)

Noble+Rudnick, et al. ApJ in Press

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Take away points

- Stellar populations of distant cluster galaxies require rapid early quenching
- We have entered the age of molecular gas studies in young clusters and proto-clusters.
- Proto-cluster galaxies have a range of gas fraction. Most are higher than field, with longer consumption timescales.
- There is large scatter in quenching efficiency and in properties of gas. Is it random or can we learn something about quenching?
- CO studies must be carried out on significant samples of clusters.